

Designing Supportive Learning Environments: The Impact of Therapy Dog Interventions in Academic Libraries

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STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

We aim to investigate the role of affective interventions in academic library environments, focusing on how therapy dog sessions during exam periods influence student stress, attention, and information engagement during learning process.

Value of the contribution

The contribution offers value by challenging traditional notions of library services, demonstrating how therapy dog sessions can better facilitate information engagement through reduced stress and improved focus during high-pressure academic periods. Our research has strong practical implications, providing theoretical support for such unconventional library services and emphasizing the need for their broader implementation to better serve academic library users.

Research outline

Therapy dog sessions in academic settings are an established practice internationally, particularly in North America and Scandinavian countries (Fenton, 2019; Schwartz, 2012; University of Ottawa, n.d.). They are most commonly implemented during exam periods, when students engage in intensive information work such as studying, knowledge consolidation, and information retention under conditions of increased stress (Bomhold, 2025; Švab, 2025). Research shows that even brief interactions can reduce stress, improve mood, and increase relaxation (Barker et al., 2017; Green & Ormsby, 2024; Jalongo & McDevitt, 2015). Importantly, students also report improved memorization of study material when preparing for exams in the presence of therapy dogs (The protégé effect, 2025). This highlights the relevance for supporting students during their learning processes under conditions of high stress and cognitive load.

As academic libraries are shifting their traditional role as providers of information resources and becoming spaces that actively support learning processes, our research aim lay in exploring the feasibility and impact of alternative, affective library services. However, therapy dog interventions in academic libraries have not yet been widely implemented in Slovenia, which provided an additional motivation for the present study. The study is guided by research questions examining how potential library users perceive therapy dog presence in higher education settings, what types of activities they would prefer, and how these interventions affect participant wellbeing. Therapy dog interventions in Slovenia are typically organized at the request of host institutions. The three academic libraries participating in this study constituted a convenience sample of institutions that had requested therapy dog visits during the preceding year. The sessions were conducted by a licensed therapy dog team comprising a qualified handler and a certified therapy dog affiliated with Tačke pomagačke, a Slovenian volunteer society for dog-assisted therapy that has been active for two decades and currently includes approximately 90 therapy dogs and their handlers (Slovenian Society for Dog-Assisted Therapy Tačke pomagačke, n.d.). The involvement of a licensed therapy dog team ensured adherence to established standards for both participant safety and animal welfare. The sessions were designed based on a literature review and experiences from other educational settings, focusing on creating an inclusive environment and incorporating relaxation activities. We presented participants with pre- and post-session questionnaires. Due to animal wellbeing considerations, sessions are conducted with a limited number of participants. In total, 26 responses were collected across all three institutions.

Participants self-reported a clear reduction in stress following therapy dog sessions, with mean wellbeing scores increasing from 3.46 before the session to 4.69 after. 23 of 26 respondents indicated that therapy dog presence would positively influence their perception of academic libraries, and almost 80% stated it would encourage more frequent visits, with nearly all expressing willingness to participate in such sessions again. Participants were also asked to list up to three emotions or associations related to therapy dog presence in academic libraries. The most frequent terms were relaxation, joy, and calmness, indicating a strong positive affective response linked to reduced stress, improved readiness for learning, and enhanced conditions for knowledge acquisition during studying.

The study is limited by a small, self-selected sample, likely skewed toward students who are positively disposed to such activities. The limited timeframe further constrains

broader applicability. Nevertheless, the findings highlight the value of therapy dog interventions, showing that they can support information engagement by improving focus, knowledge retention, and students' sense of belonging, while opening more inclusive academic library environments.

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